

Study of Bacteriological Profile and Antibiogram of Infections in Intensive Care Units of a Tertiary Care HospitalKumari Jyoti¹, Sunanda Kundu², Namrata Kumari³, Kumar Saurabh⁴¹Medical Lab Technologist, Department of Microbiology, IGIMS, Patna²Multidisciplinary Research Unit, IGIMS, Patna³Professor & HOD, Department of Microbiology, IGIMS, Patna⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Microbiology, IGIMS, Patna

Received: 14-11-2023 / Revised: 27-12-2023 / Accepted: 19-01-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background and Objective: The intensive care unit (ICU) often called as the epicentre of infections, due to its vulnerable population. It has been reported that the incidence of nosocomial infections in the intensive care unit (ICU) is about 2 to 5 times higher than in the general inpatient hospital population. The present study aims to know the causative organisms and antibiotic susceptibility of infections in intensive care units.

Methods: It is a prospective study with 300 patients with suspected infections included were included. Samples were processed as per standard guidelines and the colonies were identified according to standard biochemical tests. Antibiotic susceptibility testing was done on Muller Hinton agar using Kirby Bayers's disc diffusion test. ESBL production was tested by disc diffusion method as in CLSI phenotypic method (2017).

Conclusion: There is increase in number of infections in ICUs due to multidrug resistance organism, which is the big public health threat and challenge for both prevention and treatment of infections. Thus, the incidence rates, the causative agents and their susceptibility play a vital role in the management of infections in ICU.

Keywords: Endotracheal aspirate, ESBL, ICU.

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Introduction

Infections are a common problem for patients in intensive care units (ICUs) and are associated with substantial morbidity, mortality, and costs. [1] The intensive care unit (ICU) often is called the epicentre of infections, due to its vulnerable population and increased risk of getting infections through multiple procedures, use of invasive devices such as endotracheal intubation, central venous cannulations, mechanical ventilation (MV), and urinary catheterisation distorting the anatomical integrity. [2] ICU population has one of the highest occurrence rates of nosocomial infections (20–30% of all ICU-admissions). [3] The European Studies on Prevalence of Infections in ICU (EPIC-1 and EPIC-2) reported a high prevalence of infections in a number of European countries. [4,5] High prevalence of infections, especially nosocomial, has also been reported from medical ICUs in the United States. [6] The elderly age group, APACHE-2 scores and high prevalence of co-morbid conditions are associated with infections in ICU. [4] In a study by Divatia JV et al. on Infections in Intensive Care in India showed, 35.9% of culture positive isolates within the positive isolates, 68.9% were Gram-negative organisms, 15.9% were Gram-positive organisms, 7.5% fungi, 2.4% mycobacteria,

1.7% viruses, and 1.1% malarial parasites. The EPIC-II showed, 69.6% culture positive isolates, within the culture positives 47% were Gram positive, 62% were Gram negative, Anaerobes were 4.4%, Fungi were 18.5%, Viral/parasite 2.6%, Others 2.2%. [4] Infections in the intensive care unit (ICU) are classified into Community-acquired, Hospital-acquired, ICU acquired. The EPIC-2 study showed that lungs were the most common site of infection, accounting for 64% of infections, followed by abdominal (19%) and bloodstream infections (15%). The risk of acquiring the infection in critically ill patients in the ICU is around 18%. [4] The three likely portals of entry are more importantly is inhalation, ingestion, and contact. Spread of infection through contacts is by intubation and use of nasogastric tube in-situ, physical contact with the patient or with the patient's devices. [7] It has been reported that the incidence of nosocomial infections in the intensive care unit (ICU) is about 2 to 5 times higher than in the general inpatient hospital population. [8,9] As infection in ICU can be both Community acquired and hospital acquired. Community acquired Infection such as meningitis and pneumonia may cause potentially life threatening infection. Even with the availability of

potent newer antibiotics, the mortality rate due to acute bacterial meningitis remains significantly high in India and other developing countries, which is nearly 22%. [10] The common causes of bacterial meningitis in adults are *Neisseria meningitidis*, *Streptococcus pneumoniae* and *Listeria monocytogenes*, and *staphylococci* and *Haemophilus influenzae* is rarely seen in an adult, in case Hib vaccination during childhood [10]. Community acquired pneumonia (CAP) defined as pneumonia not acquired in a hospital or a long-term care facility. The overall annual incidence of CAP ranges from 5 to 11 per 1,000 persons, with more cases occurring in the winter months. [11] Survey of 16 studies of severe CAP showed, *S. pneumoniae* in 12–38%, *Legionella* sp., in 0–30 %; *Staphylococcus aureus* in 1–18% and Gram negative enteric bacilli was seen in 2–34%. [12] But in India *Str. pneumoniae* (35.3%) is the most common isolate, followed by *Staphylococcus aureus* (23.5%), *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (20.5%), and *Haemophilus influenzae* (8.8%). [13] There is a great need for local resistance prevalence data in order to guide empirical prescription and to identify areas in which medical need for new agents is needed. Hence, this study is undertaken to determine the bacteriological profile of organisms causing infections in intensive care units.

Objectives

- To study the antibiotic susceptibility patterns of the isolated organisms.
- To screen for ESBL (extended spectrum beta lactamase) producing bacterial isolates.
- To screen for MRSA (Methicillin Resistant *Staphylococcus Aureus*) producing bacterial isolates.

Material and Methods

It is a prospective cross-sectional study of bacterial isolates from patients admitted to intensive care unit with clinical signs and symptoms of infection, Total 300 patients with suspected infections included were included. Samples were processed as per standard guidelines and the colonies were identified according to standard biochemical tests. Antibiotic susceptibility testing was done on Muller Hinton agar using Kirby Bauers's disc diffusion test. ESBL production was tested by disc diffusion method as in CLSI phenotypic method. Department of Microbiology, Indira Gandhi Institute of Medical Sciences

Table 1:

Demographics	
Age (years)	45.7 ± 14
Male (n=%)	192(64%)
ICU (days)	8.3 ± 5.6
Male(n=%)	Female(n=%)
192(64)	108(36)

Patna, Bihar. Study duration of Two Years.

Inclusion Criteria: Patients with clinical symptoms and signs of infections admitted in intensive care units are included in study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Paediatric and neonatal intensive care units.
- Cases referred to the hospital from outside.
- Patient with HIV, HCV, HBV Co infection

Fungal Infection: Gram stain was performed on the samples (endotracheal aspirate, pus) and interpreted for the presence and numbers of WBCs and bacterial and fungal elements and presence of bacteria.

Processing and Identification: Samples were sent to laboratory from intensive care units as per the infection involved, under aseptic precautions. Blood Paired blood sample of quantity 10-20 ml inoculated into BHI broth and are incubated 35°-37°C & routinely inspected twice a day for the first 3 days and are incubated up to 7 days. Subcultured on MacConkey's and 5% sheep blood agar plates after 24, 48 and 72 hr. The plates will be incubated for 24hr at 37°C and also the bottles were examined daily for visible sign of growth in the bottle. Further processing of positive blood cultures Gram-stain a thin smear from the broth or agar in case growth. Subculture to agar media and biochemical tests were performed based on the Gramstain Results.

Antibiotic Susceptibility Testing: According to CLSI guidelines (81), HiMedia disks for the following antibiotics were used Gram negative organisms: Ampicillin (10µg), Amoxicillin-Clavulanate (20/10µg) Gentamicin (10µg), Amikacin (30µg), Piperacillin-Tazobactam (100/10µg), Cefepime (30µg), Cefoxitin (30µg), Cefotaxime (30µg), Ciprofloxacin (5µg), Ceftriaxone (30µg), Imipenem (10µg), Ertapenem (10µg), Cotrimoxazole (1.25/23.75µg), Aztreonam (30µg), Ceftazidime (30µg), Chloramphenicol (30µg), Tetracycline (30µg), Tigecycline (15µg), Levofloxacin (5µg).

Gram positive organisms: Penicillin (10units), cefoxitin (30µg), Tetracycline (30µg), Ampicillin (10µg), Ciprofloxacin (5µg), Linezolid (30µg).

Results

Demographic Data of the Study

Showing Gender distribution in the study

Pie chart showing distribution of gender distribution study.

Chart 1:

Showing different isolates from the study group

Table 2:

Name	N=429	Percentage
Endotracheal aspirate	174	40.4%
Blood	121	28%
Urine	125	29%
Pus	9	2.1%

Graph showing different samples from study group

Endotracheal aspirate Urine Blood Pus

Endotracheal aspirate(40%) was the commonest sample followed by,urine(27%),blood(28%) and pus(2%) total culture positive among isolates

Culture positive	Culture negative
26%(112)	74%(317)

Total of 429 clinical samples were collected from 300 patients. Among 429 samples,112 (26%) samples were culture positive, and predominantly culture was positive from endotracheal aspirate (74%), followed by urine (14%), 9.6% from blood (9.6%) and skin and soft tissue (5%).

Growth from aerobic culture of endotracheal aspirate sample

	Number (n=174)	Percentage
Culture negative	91	52%
Culture positive	83	48%

Total number of 174 samples were processed and aerobic culture was positive I 48%(n=83).

Most common organism isolated from aerobic culture were *Klebsiella* sp(40%) followed by *Acinetobacter* sps (35%), *Escherichia coli*(13%), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*(9%), *Staphylococcus aureus*(1%).

Antibiotic resistant pattern seen in of *Klebsiella* Spp endotracheal aspirate sample.

	Amc	Gen	Cot	Pit	Imp	Cip	CTR	Tgc	C	At	Te
Sensitive	0	21	14	12	27	9	14	19	18	14	16
Resistant	33	12	19	21	6	24	19	0	3	19	3

Total of 33 *Klebsiella* sp (both *Klebsiella oxytoca* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*)

Almost all the isolates were resistant to amoxicillin-clavulanate (100%). 44% of *Klebsiella* sp were sensitive to 3rd generation cephalosporins, 65% *Klebsiella* sp. was sensitive to amikacin. Highest sensitivity was seen in imipenem(82%), and tigecycline(100%)

Organism isolated from blood sample.

	Numbers (n=8)	Percentage
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	3	37.5%
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	3	37.5%
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	2	25%

In Total of 121 blood samples were processed and 8 (6.6%) samples were culture positive which yielded *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus*.

total of 9 samples were received and among them 5 (55.5%) samples were culture positive and organism isolated were *Escherichia coli* (n=2), *Klebsiella* sps. (n=1), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*(n=1), and *Staphylococcus aureus* (n=1). All the isolates from skin and soft tissue were sensitive to amikacin and gentamicin.

Phenotypic Detection of ESBL by CDT

Total of 65 isolates were screened for aztreonam and cefotaxime and ceftazidime and 34 isolates were sensitive.

Rest of 32 isolates were tested with cefotaxime and cefotaxime clavulanic acid and ceftazidime and ceftazidime clavulanic acid by CDT. 12(38%) samples were showed positive for ESBL by combined disk diffusion

Discussion

Infections are one of the most important causes of mortality in the world, more so in low and lower-

middle income countries. The intensive care units constitute less than 10% of total hospital beds but they harbour up to 30% of the nosocomial infections in the hospital. Infections in ICU consists of both community acquired and hospital acquired. With the emergence of multidrug resistant strains the early identification and diagnosis are of utmost concern. Hence, understanding the bacteriology and antibiogram of infections in ICU is of immense importance for better management. In this study the mean age of the patients were 45.7 ± 14 years and there were 192 men (64%) and 108 women (36%).

Prevalence of microbiologic isolates in Intensive Care Units

A total of 429 samples were received from 300 patient, total culture positive among samples were 26% (112) which is similar to the study done by Ghanshani, et al where culture positive was 28% (623). But the culture positive seen in study by Vincent et al⁴ showed 38.3%, 35.9% culture was positive in Divatia JV et a which was higher than the present study, these findings may be due to the relatively small sample size of the present study.

Prevalence of microbiologic isolates in ICU from different parts of India

Studyn (%)	Vincent et al.	Ghanshani et al.	In this study
Culture positive	505(38.3%)	623(28%)	112(26%)
Gram negative organism	376(74.5%)	475(76%)	106(95%)
Gram positive organism	168(33.3%)	99(16%)	6(5%)

Gram-negative bacteria were predominant and included 38% of *Klebsiella spp*, 26% of *Acinetobacter spp*, 21% of *Escherichia coli* and 10% *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus* was isolated in 5%. The findings are similar to the study done by Patwardhan et al.

The study conducted by Ghanshani, et al showed similar organisms but most frequently isolated were *Acinetobacter baumannii* (20.9%), *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (19.7%), *Escherichia coli* (18.3%), and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*(14.0%).

Prevalence rates of infections in ICU

The infections rate was maximum in the skin and soft tissue infections (55%), pneumonia (48%) followed by UTI (12%), bloodstream infection (6%). VAP (74%) followed by urinary tract infection (14%) were the most commonly seen HAIs in present study, and is similar to study conducted by EPIC II ⁴ and Michael *et al.* [14] but other studies

conducted by Lee *et al.*, [15] Richards *et al.* [16] and Mythri *et al.* [17] *et al.*, the incidence of UTI was most common followed by pneumonia and blood stream infections.

Prevalence rates of infections in ICU reported from other studies.

	Pneumonia (%)	Bloodstreaminfection (%)	Urinary tractinfection (%)
Vincent <i>et al.</i>	46.9	12.0	17.6
Kallel <i>et al.</i>	58.2	18.2	14.5
Markogiannakis <i>et al.</i>	25.3	36.1	9.5
In this study	74	6	12

Different isolates obtained from urine samples in various studies.

Study	Organisms isolated
Mojtahedzadeh <i>et al.</i>	<i>K. pneumonia</i> (4%), followed by <i>E. Coli</i> (21%), <i>CoNS</i> (18%), and <i>P. Aeruginosa</i> (18%)
Vinoth M <i>et al.</i>	<i>Escherichia coli</i> (22%), <i>Klebsiella sp</i> (18%), <i>Enterobacter</i> (8%), <i>Staph. Aureus</i> (6%)
In this study	<i>Escherichia coli</i> (62%), <i>Klebsiella spp</i> (31%), <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (6%).

12% occurrence of catheter-associated UTI (CAUTI) with *Escherichia coli*(62%), followed by *Klebsiella sp*(31%), *MRSA* (5%) similar findings were seen in study conducted by Vinoth M *et al* and Prajapati *et al.* 28% was occurrence of CAUTI in Mojtahedzadeh *et al.* which was higher than the present study this was due to definition of bacteriuria was $>10^4$ CFU/ml. Gender was not a risk factor for catheter-associated bacteriuria in present study.

Showing incidence of antibiotic sensitivity for isolated organism

	Our study	Shalini <i>et al</i> 2009	Prajapati <i>et al</i>
Amikacin	66.66%	87.41	85.7
Nitrofurantoin	74%	81.12	78.57
Norfloxacin	33%	72.73	71.42

In present study, most of the *Acinetobacter sp*(100%) were resistant to ciprofloxacin and 70% to Gentamicin, 58% to Imipenem. Maximum number of *Acinetobacter sp.* were sensitive to levofloxacin(65%) and ceftazidime(60%). In study conducted by Goel *et al.* ⁹⁵ Showed *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was resistant to Gentamicin (100%), Aztreonam (88.23%), Ciprofloxacin and Amikacin (82.35%), Imipenem (47.06%), Ceftazidime (35.29%) and Piperacillin-tazobactam (23.53%). In the present study, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was showed 85% sensitive to Imipenem, 72% sensitive to amikacin, piperacillin tazobactam and ceftazidime ESBL screening was done on *Escherichia coli* (36%) and *Klebsiella*(54%) and it was found that 38% of isolates showed ESBL production. These findings were similar to the study conducted by Vasumathi A *et al.* (39.5%). But study conducted by Deepti *et al.* showed prevalence of 11.7% in their study population. Most of the ESBL strains were sensitive to amikacin and gentamicin. With the rise in the multidrug resistant strains and the emergence of ESBL producers it is essential to treat the infections in ICU.

Conclusion

Infections are a common problem for patients in intensive care units (ICUs) and are associated with substantial morbidity, mortality, and costs. Both primary infections and secondary infections rates are high in ICUs. In the present study all the patients with clinical signs and symptoms of infections in ICUs are included. The study showed VAP was the most common infections followed by CAUTI and blood stream infections.

The majority of the samples obtained from patients yielded cultures of

Enterobacteriaceae and Non Fermenters: In present study, most common organism associated with infection were *Klebsiella sp.* and *Acinetobacter sp.*, *Escherichia coli* and other species like, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* *Staphylococcus aureus*, were less frequently isolated.

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